

THERMAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PHASE CHANGE CONDUCTIVE POLYMER COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY

Phase change materials based on soft paraffin wax blended with polyethylenes and mixed with copper powder were studied in this work. The purpose of the study was to form composites that can store energy and conduct heat. The influence of wax and copper contents on the morphology as well as thermal, mechanical and conductivity properties was investigated.

Keywords: Wax; Polyethylene; Copper; Composites; Phase change materials

EXPERIMENTAL

LDPE and LLDPE were supplied in pellet form by Sasol Polymers. LDPE has an MFI of 7.0 g/10 min (ASTM D-1238), a melting point of 106 °C, a molecular weight of 96 000 g mol⁻¹, and a density of 0.918 g cm⁻³ and LLDPE has an MFI of 1.0 g/10 min (ASTM D-1238), a molecular weight of 191 600 g mol⁻¹, a melting point of 124 °C, and a density of 0.924 g cm⁻³. HDPE was supplied in pellet form by DOW Chemicals. It has an MFI of 8 g/10 min (ASTM D-1238), a molecular weight of 168 000 g mol⁻¹, a melting point of 130 °C, and a density of 0.954 g cm⁻³. Soft paraffin wax (M3 wax) was supplied in powder form by Sasol Polymers. It is a paraffin wax consisting of approximately 99% of straight chain hydrocarbons and few branched chains, and it is primarily used in the candle-making industry. It has an average molar mass of 440 g mol⁻¹ and a carbon distribution between C15 and C78. Its density is 0.90 g cm⁻³ and it has a melting point range around 40-60 °C. All blends were blended by mixing the polymer and wax in a Brabender Plastograph at different ratios, and mixed in a 55 cm³ mixing chamber at 160 °C and a speed of 70 rpm for 15 min. After the preparation, the samples were melt pressed at same temperature and time. Blends with wax concentrations ranging between 0 and 50% by volume were prepared.

DSC analyses were done in a Perkin-Elmer Pyris-1 differential scanning calorimeter under flowing nitrogen (flow rate 20 mL min⁻¹). The instrument was computer controlled and calculations were done using Pyris software. It was calibrated using the onset temperatures of melting of indium and zinc standards, as well as the melting enthalpy of indium. Samples (5-10 mg) were sealed in aluminium pans and heated from -40 to 160 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹, and cooled at the same rate.

For the second scan, the samples were heated and cooled under the same conditions. The peak temperatures of melting and crystallization, as well as melting and crystallization enthalpies were determined from the second scan. All DSC measurements were repeated three times for each sample. The melting and crystallization temperatures, as well as enthalpies, are reported as average values with standard deviations.

TGA analysis was carried out on a Perkin-Elmer TGA7 thermogravimetric analyser. Samples ranging between 5 and 10 mg were heated from 30 to 650 °C at a heating rate of 20 °C min⁻¹ under flowing nitrogen (flow rate 20 mL min⁻¹). The instrument was computer controlled and calculations were done using Pyris software.

A Hounsfield H5KS universal testing machine was used for the tensile analysis of 1 mm thick samples. The dumbbell samples, with a gauge length of 24 mm, were stretch at a speed of 50 mm min⁻¹ under a cell load of 250.0 N. About nine test samples were cut using a dumbbell cutter and they were all tested. Stress-strain curves that indicated sample deficiencies were ignored during the final calculations of the tensile properties.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DSC analysis of PE/wax blends and PE/wax/Cu blend composites

The DSC heating curves obtained for the different PEs and the wax are presented in Fig. 1, while those for the different PE/wax blends are shown in Figures 2 – 4. The melting peak temperatures, as well as melting and crystallization enthalpies are summarized in Table 1. The wax shows a melting peak at 58 °C, with a peak shoulder at 33 °C. The DSC heating curves of the LDPE/wax blends show two clearly defined endothermic events. The first event between 30 and 70 °C consists of a peak shoulder at about 33 °C and two overlapping peaks between 45 and 70 °C. The first event is in the

Figure 1 DSC heating curves of pure polyolefins and pure wax

same temperature region as the melting peak of pure wax, but its shape is different. When the wax content in the blend is lower, the peaks between 45 and 70 °C shows clearly defined peak maxima. However, at higher wax contents, the lower temperature peak becomes more dominant, reducing the higher temperature peak to a peak shoulder. This indicates that the shorter LDPE chains and/or branches probably co-crystallized with the wax, but that this effect becomes less pronounced with increasing wax content. The melting enthalpy values of the LDPE/wax blends are the same within experimental error than those calculated using the additive rule in Equation 1. This confirms that there was no wax leakage from the LDPE matrix, which is a good observation for shape-stabilized phase change materials. The explanation of the DSC results in terms of co-crystallization of LDPE/wax blends, at low wax contents, is in line with that given by Hato and Luyt [1]. They envisaged co-crystallization of LDPE with both un-oxidized and oxidized hard paraffin wax in their study of the thermal fractionation of PE/wax blends. The second thermal event in Fig. 2 is associated with the melting of LDPE crystallites. The melting peak temperatures of LDPE in the blends are significantly lower than that of pure LDPE (Table 1 and Fig. 2), and the temperatures further decrease with increasing wax content. This behaviour is probably the result of the molten wax which acts as a plasticizer in the LDPE matrix.

$$\Delta H_m^{add} = \Delta H_{m,PE} w_{PE} + \Delta H_{m,w} w_w \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta H_{m,PE}$, $\Delta H_{m,w}$, ΔH_m^{add} are the specific enthalpies of melting of PE, wax and blends, and w_{PE} , w_w are the weight fractions of PE and wax in the blends.

Figure 2 DSC heating curves of LDPE, wax and LDPE/wax blends

Table 1 DSC results for polyethylene/wax blends

v/v	T _{p,m} / °C	ΔH _m ^{obs} / J g ⁻¹	ΔH _m ^{add} / J g ⁻¹	T _{p,c} / °C
LDPE/wax				
100/0	106.8 ± 1.5	75.4 ± 6.2	75.4	91.7 ± 0.6
70/30	58.2 ^a ± 5.0	104.7 ± 3.7	104.4	55.6 ^a ± 0.9
	59.7 ^b ± 1.2			87.4 ^b ± 0.9
	100.4 ^c ± 2.8			
60/40	55.5 ^a ± 0.7	114.0 ± 10.9	113.6	55.8 ^a ± 0.2
	96.9 ^b ± 3.2			87.8 ^b ± 1.8
50/50	55.0 ^a ± 0.6	111.0 ± 8.6	106.3	56.0 ^a ± 0.6
	97.6 ^b ± 2.1			86.0 ^b ± 0.5
0/100	58.4 ^a ± 1.2	172.2 ± 0.1	172.2	53.1 ± 0.4
LLDPE/wax				
100/0	126.7 ± 2.1	86.9 ± 1.0	86.9	109.6 ± 0.9
70/30	57.3 ^a ± 1.6	108.5 ± 10.3	111.7	53.2 ^a ± 0.9
	121.8 ^b ± 0.9			105.7 ^b ± 0.9
60/40	54.5 ^a ± 1.1	104.9 ± 15	120.6	49.8 ^a ± 0.7
	119.8 ^b ± 1.1			105.2 ^b ± 1.1
50/50	57.2 ^a ± 0.6	130.3 ± 8.2	130.0	49.8 ^a ± 0.9
	120.8 ^b ± 1.1			103.8 ^b ± 0.6
0/100	58.4 ^a ± 1.2	172.2 ± 0.1	172.2	53.1 ± 0.4
HDPE/wax				
100/0	134.7 ± 0.5	149.3 ± 9.7	149.3	113.9 ± 1.1
70/30	56.1 ^a ± 0.1	150.9 ± 15	156.2	51.1 ^a ± 0.1
	124.6 ^b ± 1.8			110.2 ^b ± 1.8
60/40	56.4 ^a ± 0.4	153.2 ± 9.9	158.5	51.1 ^a ± 0.6
	124.1 ^b ± 2.3			110.2 ^b ± 0.4
50/50	57.1 ^a ± 0.1	148.4 ± 8.9	160.8	50.8 ^a ± 0.9
	124.1 ^b ± 0.3			109.6 ^b ± 1.1
0/100	58.4 ^a ± 1.2	172.2 ± 0.1	172.2	53.1 ± 0.4

T_{p,m}, ΔH_m^{obs}, ΔH_m^{calc}, T_{p,c} are melting peak temperature, observed melting enthalpy, calculated melting enthalpy, and crystallization peak temperature, while a and b indicate the first and second peak maxima in the wax melting peak

The results of the DSC analyses of LLDPE/wax blends are summarized in Table 1 and presented in Fig. 3. The DSC heating curve of pure wax shows a melting peak at 58 °C, with a peak shoulder at 33 °C. The DSC heating curves of the blends show two clearly defined endothermic events. The first event consists of a peak shoulder at about 33 °C and a single peak at about 58 °C. The second event is associated with the melting of LLDPE crystallites. The melting peak temperatures of LLDPE in the blends are lower than that of pure LLDPE, and the temperatures further decrease with increasing wax content. This behaviour is probably the result of the molten wax which acts as a plasticizer in the LLDPE matrix. Looking at Figs. 2 and 3 it seems as if there are smaller decreases in the melting temperatures of LLDPE than in the case of LDPE. The reason is most probably that the paraffin wax, which has been found to have a much lower miscibility with LDPE than with LLDPE [1-3], probably crystallizes separately in

the amorphous phase of LDPE, while part of the wax may co-crystallize with the LLDPE chains. The wax that crystallizes separately will melt before the polyethylene, and the molten wax will act as a plasticizer. However, the wax that is co-crystallized with the polyethylene chains will melt at the same temperature as the polyethylene, and can therefore not contribute to the plasticizing effect of the wax. Since the wax probably has a higher miscibility (more co-crystallization) with LLDPE than with LDPE, there will be less crystalline wax in the amorphous regions of LLDPE and therefore the plasticizing effect and reduction in melting temperature of the polymer will be less obvious.

Figure 3 DSC heating curves of LLDPE, wax and LLDPE/wax blends

The melting peak temperatures, as well as the melting and crystallization enthalpies of the HDPE/wax blends are shown in Fig. 4 and summarized in Table 1. The curve for pure wax is the same than previously discussed. The DSC heating curves of the HDPE/wax blends show two clearly defined endothermic events. The first event consists of a peak shoulder at about 33 °C, and a single peak at about 58 °C. The second event is associated with the melting of the HDPE crystallites. In this case the decrease in melting peak temperature is higher than in the case of LDPE and LLDPE. According to Hato and Luyt [1] paraffin wax has the lowest miscibility with HDPE, and it will therefore have the strongest influence on the melting temperature of the polymer. As in the case of LDPE and LLDPE the observed and calculated (according to Eq. 1) melting enthalpies are the same within experimental error, indicating that no wax leakage occurred during sample preparation. Another possibility in case of LDPE might be that ethylene crystallization is disrupted by the wax which is less miscible and therefore forms a more segregated morphology with the wax dispersed in the polymer matrix.

The DSC peak temperatures, as well as the melting and crystallization enthalpies, of the PE/wax/Cu micro-composites are summarized in Table 2. Table 2 also contains the enthalpies calculated according to the additive rule (Eq. 1). The results show that the presence of Cu micro-particles did not significantly change the thermal

behaviour of the PE/wax blends, despite the fact that the wax seems to have a higher affinity for the copper and preferably crystallizes on the copper surface (SEM results not presented in this paper. The melting temperatures for the wax as well as all three polymers show the same changes that were observed for the blends in the absence of copper, while the melting enthalpies in all cases correspond well with those calculated according to the additive rule.

Table 2 DSC results for polyethylene/wax/Cu micro-composites

v/v	$T_{p,m} / ^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta H_m^{\text{obs}} / \text{J g}^{-1}$	$\Delta H_m^{\text{add}} / \text{J g}^{-1}$	$T_{p,c} / ^\circ\text{C}$
LDPE/wax/Cu				
100/0/0	106.8 ± 1.5	75.4 ± 6.2	75.4	91.7 ± 0.6
59/40/1	$58.1^a \pm 5.4$ $99.9^b \pm 1.2$	104.7 ± 6.8	104.0	$55.6^a \pm 0.9$ $87.4^b \pm 0.9$
57/40/3	$61.3^a \pm 0.9$ $100.6^b \pm 1.1$	87.8 ± 3.4	88.0	$55.8^a \pm 0.2$ $87.8^b \pm 1.8$
55/40/5	$60.6^s \pm 1.6$ $99.3^b \pm 0.9$	68.2 ± 9.0	79.3	$56.0^a \pm 0.6$ $86.0^b \pm 0.5$
50/40/10	$53.2^a \pm 1.6$ $98.4^b \pm 1.6$	48.3 ± 4.0	56.5	$53.8^a \pm 3.5$ $86.1^b \pm 0.5$
0/100/0	$58.4^a \pm 1.2$	172.2 ± 0.1	172.2	53.1 ± 0.4
LLDPE/wax/Cu				
100/0/0	126.7 ± 2.1	86.9 ± 1.0	86.9	109.6 ± 0.9
59/40/1	$54.9^a \pm 1.6$ $120.4^b \pm 1.8$	113.5 ± 6.6	109.5	$49.8^a \pm 0.5$ $105.5^b \pm 0.8$
57/40/3	$54.7^a \pm 1.4$ $120.6^b \pm 1.9$	89.5 ± 10.4	92.5	$49.8^a \pm 0.6$ $105.7^b \pm 0.8$
55/40/5	$54.6^a \pm 1.6$ $119.9^b \pm 1.6$	74.3 ± 9.5	80.4	$50.1^a \pm 0.5$ $105.8^b \pm 0.8$
50/40/10	$55.1^a \pm 1.6$ $120.0^b \pm 2.2$	49.5 ± 12.0	59.6	$50.1^a \pm 0.5$ $106.0^b \pm 1.0$
0/100/0	$58.4^a \pm 1.2$	172.2 ± 0.1	172.2	53.1 ± 0.4
HDPE/wax/Cu				
100/0/0	134.7 ± 0.5	149.3 ± 9.7	149.3	113.9 ± 1.1
59/40/1	$56.5^a \pm 0.6$ $123.8^b \pm 0.7$	150.0 ± 3.5	148.2	$51.8^a \pm 1.1$ $109.2^b \pm 0.4$
57/40/3	$56.5^a \pm 0.4$ $122.8^b \pm 0.4$	113.7 ± 5.0	122.2	$51.9^a \pm 0.6$ $109.7^b \pm 0.4$
55/40/5	$56.9^a \pm 0.4$ $123.5^b \pm 0.2$	91.7 ± 14.8	100.6	$51.9^a \pm 0.6$ $110.1^b \pm 0.4$
50/40/10	$56.8^a \pm 0.1$ $122.8^b \pm 1.0$	77.1 ± 5.7	78.0	$51.7^a \pm 0.1$ $110.1^b \pm 0.3$
0/100/0	$58.4^a \pm 1.2$	172.2 ± 0.1	172.2	53.1 ± 0.4

$T_{p,m}$, ΔH_m^{obs} , ΔH_m^{calc} , $T_{p,c}$ are melting peak temperature, observed melting enthalpy, calculated melting enthalpy, and crystallization peak temperature, while a and b indicate the first and second peak maxima in the wax melting peak

Figure 4 DSC heating curves of HDPE, wax and HDPE/wax blends

TGA analysis of PE/wax blends and PE/wax/Cu blend composites

The TGA results are summarized in Table 3. For all the blends the thermal stability decreases with an increase in wax content, and the PE/wax blends degrade in two clearly distinguishable steps. Such degradation behaviour is typical for immiscible blends in which the constituents have different degradation temperatures. The first degradation step is that of wax, which has a lower thermal stability than any of the polymers. The second step is associated with the polymer degradation. As reported, the short-chain fractions of wax, as well as fragments formed by chain scission, will have enough energy to leave the matrix at a lower temperature [3-6]. Thus, introducing more of the low molecular weight wax induces a gradual decrease in the temperatures at which the degradation starts. For example, when 10% mass loss was selected as point of comparison, the thermal degradation of LDPE/wax samples with 30, 40, and 50 vol. % of wax are determined as 292, 282, and 271 °C respectively, that are 150, 161, and 172 °C lower than the 443 °C of pure LDPE.

At the same level of mass loss the thermal degradation temperatures for the LLDPE/wax blends were determined as 172, 182, and 192 °C lower than the 464 °C of pure LLDPE. The same is true for HDPE/wax blends, with thermal degradation temperatures for the HDPE/wax blends 176, 171 and 195 °C lower than pure HDPE. No char yield was observed at temperatures higher than 500 °C for all the PE/wax blends. The thermal stabilities of all the PE/wax blends therefore fall below that of the pure PEs, and gradually decreases with increasing wax content. This is because soft paraffin wax has much shorter chains and is thermally less stable than the pure PEs. The thermal stability of PE/wax blends gradually decreases with increasing wax content. In all investigated polyethylenes, it can be seen that wax does influence the decomposition of the polymer phase. It was, however, difficult to establish definite trends and therefore no conclusion can be drawn from this.

Table 3 Temperatures of 10 and 50% degradation of PE/wax blends

v/v	T ₁₀ / °C	T ₅₀ / °C
LDPE/wax		
100/0	443.3	476.3
70/30	292.9	468.8
60/40	282.4	439.4
50/50	271.1	-
100/0	262.4	341.4
LLDPE/wax		
100/0	464.6	486.1
70/30	292.9	479.4
60/40	282.4	469.1
50/50	271.1	-
100/0	262.4	341.4
HDPE/wax		
100/0	467.0	493.0
70/30	290.8	478.8
60/40	294.8	478.8
50/50	271.9	-
100/0	262.4	341.4

Table 4 Temperatures of 10, 20 and 50% degradation, of PE/wax/Cu micro-composites

v/v	T ₁₀ / °C	T ₂₀ / °C	T ₅₀ / °C	Wt. % residue	Wt. % Cu in sample
LDPE/wax/Cu					
60/40/0	282.4	313.4	439.4	0.0	0.0
59/40/1	289.9	326.9	470.9	7.8	7.0
57/40/3	293.0	334.0	477.0	21.5	23.6
55/40/5	292.8	337.8	478.8	30.4	33.9
50/40/10	298.3	354.3	-	41.8	42.0
LLDPE/wax/Cu					
60/40/0	282.4	327.1	469.1	0.0	0.0
59/40/1	292.7	329.7	479.7	9.7	8.7
57/40/3	295.9	339.9	484.9	24.4	24.0
55/40/5	295.9	341.9	488.9	34.4	34.0
50/40/10	303.0	427.0	-	53.1	51.0
HDPE/wax/Cu					
60/40/0	294.8	340.8	478.8	0.0	0.0
59/40/1	294.7	333.7	478.7	9.1	8.9
57/40/3	289.2	329.2	484.2	22.7	21.0
55/40/5	292.8	340.2	487.2	31.7	30.3
50/40/10	298.3	404.0	-	53.7	51.9

The thermal stability results of PE/wax/Cu micro-composites at constant 40 vol. % of wax are summarized in Table 4. The composites degraded in two clearly distinguishable steps, similar to those observed for the PE/wax blends. The thermal stabilities of the composites generally increase with increasing Cu content, and they are higher than those of the corresponding PE/wax blends, although this effect is less pronounced for the HDPE/wax/Cu micro-composites. The higher thermal stabilities are probably due to a combination of the immobilization of PE and wax free radicals and volatile degradation products, since the wax decomposes first, and since it is concentrated around the Cu particles.

Tensile analysis of PE/wax blends and PE/wax/Cu blend composites

The data presented in Table 5 shows that blending wax with PE significantly influences the mechanical properties of the materials. In all the investigated PE/wax blends, the stress at break decreased with an increase in wax content. The main reason for this decrease is due to the increased amount of low molecular weight wax, which deteriorates the tensile strength of the blend. Wax itself has very poor tensile properties and the wax crystals in the amorphous phase of the respective polymers act as defect points for the initiation and propagation of stress cracking. Increasing wax content had a more significant influence on the tensile strength of LDPE, probably because of the higher amorphous content in this polymer. Lower values of stress at break were also observed by Mtshali *et al.* [6], after blending LDPE with wax. They showed that the changes at lower wax concentrations are within experimental error, but at higher wax concentrations significant deterioration of the basic properties of the materials were observed.

Table 5 Mechanical properties of the PE/wax blends

v/v	$\sigma_b \pm S\sigma_b$ / MPa	$\epsilon_b \pm S\epsilon_b$ / %	E \pm sE / MPa
LDPE/wax			
100/0	10.1 \pm 0.5	336 \pm 0.0	121 \pm 8.0
70/30	9.0 \pm 0.2	30.0 \pm 4.7	163 \pm 14.0
60/40	9.1 \pm 0.6	19.0 \pm 9.4	185 \pm 12.0
50/50	5.4 \pm 0.5	4.9 \pm 0.7	192 \pm 4.0
LLDPE/wax			
100/0	25.7 \pm 1.4	1054 \pm 3.0	123 \pm 1.0
70/30	12.6 \pm 1.3	610 \pm 21	175 \pm 4.0
60/40	8.4 \pm 0.9	570 \pm 18	166 \pm 5.0
50/50	7.7 \pm 1.3	542 \pm 47	212 \pm 24
HDPE/Cu			
100/0	15.6 \pm 5.3	792 \pm 3	566 \pm 8
70/30	10.3 \pm 2.2	301 \pm 30	378 \pm 18
60/40	8.6 \pm 4.1	254 \pm 5	325 \pm 42
50/50	7.8 \pm 6.3	101 \pm 34	314 \pm 12

σ_b is stress at break and $S\sigma_b$ is the standard deviation, ϵ_b is elongation at break, $S\epsilon_b$ is the standard deviation, E is Young's modulus and sE is the standard deviation

An increase in wax content results in a decrease in elongation at break of all the investigated blends. This can also be explained by the wax crystals acting as defect points for the initiation and propagation of stress cracking. Elongation at break is also influenced by the immiscibility of the components. Since there is phase separation in all the blends, the materials loses drawability and elongation at break strongly decreases.

An increase Young's modulus with an increase in wax content is observed for the LDPE and LLDPE blends, indicating that the modulus of the wax is higher than that of both these polymers. This is probably associated with its higher degree of crystallinity. The degree of crystallinity of wax, LDPE and LLDPE are 59, 26 and 30%. There is an interaction between the crystalline and amorphous regions of the polyethylenes, giving rise to the elongation energy being transmitted from the amorphous to the crystalline phase. The presence of the wax may affect this energy transfer, which may be responsible for the increase in stiffness of the polyethylene/wax blends. In contrast with the observations on LDPE/wax and LLDPE/wax blends, the moduli of the HDPE/wax blends decreased with increasing wax content. Since the wax has a lower crystallinity than HDPE, the modulus (which depends on the sample crystallinity) decreases with increasing wax content.

The tensile data for the PE/wax/Cu composites are summarized in Table 6. The presence of copper powder at constant wax content causes an increase in tensile strength for LDPE and LLDPE at low Cu contents, followed by a decrease as the Cu content in the composites increases. The reason for the initial increase in tensile strength is not clear, but the decrease is probably the result of wax-covered Cu particles that form defect centres in the amorphous phase of the polymer. The poor mechanical properties of the wax, as well as the fact that wax seems to have weaker interaction with the polymer than Cu (the mechanical behaviour of composites depends on the quality of adhesion between matrix and filler, and in this case the filler is wax-covered Cu particles), will also contribute to the observed decrease in tensile strength with increasing Cu content. According to Nielsen [7] and Kunori [8] a strong interfacial adhesion between the dispersed and continuous phases produces a high stress at break in the composite. The HDPE/wax/Cu composites show very little change in tensile strength with increasing Cu content, similar to the HDPE/Cu microcomposites. This trend can therefore also be explained in a similar way. Orientational hardening of the polymer matrix also contributes to a decrease in the tensile strength of the composite. The smallest decrease in tensile strength is observed for LDPE and HDPE, where no orientational hardening was observed even for pure polymer. In all these cases no reinforcing effect of the filler was observed. The observed trends in elongation at break are the same as for stress at break and may be explained in a similar way.

Table 6 Mechanical properties of the PE/wax/Cu micro-composites

v/v	$\sigma_b \pm S\sigma_b$ / MPa	$\epsilon_b \pm S\epsilon_b$ / %	E \pm sE / MPa
LDPE/wax/Cu			
60/40/0	9.1 \pm 0.6	19.0 \pm 9.4	185 \pm 12.0
59/40/1	9.4 \pm 0.1	20.6 \pm 0.1	183 \pm 11
57/40/3	8.9 \pm 0.2	16.8 \pm 0.4	207 \pm 0
55/40/5	8.4 \pm 0.2	11.4 \pm 2.9	179 \pm 3
50/40/10	6.8 \pm 0.9	4.3 \pm 1.2	271 \pm 19
45/40/15	4.7 \pm 1.4	3.6 \pm 1.1	226 \pm 33
LLDPE/wax/Cu			
60/40/0	8.4 \pm 0.9	570 \pm 18	166 \pm 5.0
59/40/1	10.4 \pm 2.0	683 \pm 84	149 \pm 5
57/40/3	9.4 \pm 0.2	532 \pm 29	169 \pm 7
55/40/5	7.7 \pm 0.3	524 \pm 46	193 \pm 6
50/40/10	7.0 \pm 0.1	153.5 \pm 5.9	199 \pm 10
45/40/15	7.1 \pm 3.1	13.7 \pm 3.1	250 \pm 18
HDPE/wax/Cu			
60/40/0	8.6 \pm 4.1	247 \pm 140	325 \pm 42
59/40/1	8.1 \pm 5.5	35.7 \pm 4.1	353 \pm 31
57/40/3	10.0 \pm 4.8	27.8 \pm 4.1.	354 \pm 32
55/40/5	10.2 \pm 2.7	15.5 \pm 8.1	351 \pm 1
50/40/10	11.1 \pm 0.6	14.8 \pm 4.4	304 \pm 18
45/40/15	9.0 \pm 1.0	10.4 \pm 4.7	300 \pm 8

σ_b is stress at break and $S\sigma_b$ is the standard deviation, ϵ_b is elongation at break, $S\epsilon_b$ is the standard deviation, E is Young's modulus and sE is the standard deviation

Young's modulus increases with an increase in filler content at constant wax concentration for the LDPE/wax/Cu and LLDPE/wax/Cu composites, but it slightly decreases for the HDPE/wax/Cu composites. The reason for drop in Young's modulus of HDPE/wax/Cu micro-composites is probably caused by insufficient interaction between HDPE and the wax-covered Cu particles, which increases chain mobility in the vicinity of the filler. The values are higher for the LLDPE than for the LDPE matrices. This is in line with the known crystallinities of the respective polyethylenes. The HDPE composites have higher Young's modulus values than the LDPE and LLDPE composites, because of the higher crystallinity of HDPE.

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